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Assessing the Factors Behind Poor Commodity Trading among West African States

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Abstract

This study examines the factors responsible for poor commodity trading among West African states, despite the region's vast natural resource endowment. Using panel data covering ECOWAS member countries from 2010 to 2023, the study employs a modified gravity model and panel estimation techniques to analyse the determinants of intra-regional commodity trade. The findings reveal that economic size positively influences commodity trade, while distance, non-tariff barriers, exchange rate volatility, and insecurity significantly constrain trade flows. Trade-related infrastructure, institutional quality, and political stability were found to enhance commodity trading across the region. The results underscore that weak commodity trade in West Africa is driven more by structural, institutional, and policy-related constraints than by production capacity. The study concludes that improving infrastructure, governance, security, and trade facilitation is essential for strengthening regional commodity trade and maximising the benefits of regional integration initiatives such as ECOWAS and the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA).

Keywords: Commodity Trade; Intra-Regional Trade; West Africa; Trade Barriers; Infrastructure; Institutions; Gravity Model; ECOWAS

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Commodity trade has continued to play a very significant role in the growth of economies, structural change, and integration of regions in developing countries. In West Africa, the national economies are based on commodities, especially agriculture goods, solid minerals, and crude oil that take up a significant portion of both export income and jobs (UNCTAD, 2023; Adekoya et al., 2025; Musa et al., 2024). In spite of this endowment, the level of commodity trading between states in the West African region is still low as compared to its production capacity and with the rest of the regional blocs like the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and the Southern African Development Community (SADC) (World Bank, 2022). This abundance with poor trade performance poses significant questions on the true reasons behind poor commodity exchange in the region.

It is a well-known fact that intra-regional trade is one of the tools used to increase economic resilience, decrease susceptibility to external shocks, and additional value addition via a regional value chain (African Development Bank [AfDB], 2021). The intra-regional trade ratio that was present in West

Africa, however, has traditionally been lower than 15 per cent, and even less of its share is represented by the commodity trade (ECOWAS Commission, 2020). The majority of West African states are still exporting primary production to extra-regional destinations in raw or semi-processed conditions and importing finished or processed goods, which contributes to the trend of dependency in trade and restricts industrial development (UN Economic Commission for Africa [UNECA], 2022).

A number of studies have blamed structural, institutional, infrastructural and policy related factors as responsible in the poor commodity trading which occurs between these states of West Africa. In more structurally constraining ways, complementary trade is not feasible due to the similarities in export baskets in different countries, which are characterized by unprocessed agricultural goods and extractive goods (Imbs et al., 2019; Ismail et al., 2024). There is competition and not trade among countries especially on the commodities of cocoa, cotton, groundnuts and crude oil. This undiversification of exports restricts the exchange of regional commodities and undermines the opportunities of creation of regional value chains (Hausmann et al., 2014; Magaji et al., 2022).

The institutional and policy constraints also add to poor performance in commodity trading (Temitope & Magaji, 2023; Musa et al., 2022) Despite the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) having put up trade liberalisation schemes and protocols on free movement of goods, implementation is still weak and unequal between the member states (ECOWAS Commission, 2020). Constant non-tariff obstacles such as customs delays, informal fees, and inconsistent standards of products and fragmented regulations are major contributors to increased transaction costs and inhibit trade across borders in the trade of commodities (World Bank, 2021). Border inefficiencies in most instances do nullify the potential benefits of trade tariff reductions and has rendered formal trade channels unattractive to small- and medium-scale commodity traders.

The other significant limitation to successful commodity trading in West Africa is the infrastructure deficits. The lack of competitiveness of commodity markets in the region is caused by poor road and rail networks, limited storage and warehousing facilities, inefficient ports, and insufficient energy supply (AfDB, 2021). In landlocked nations, including Niger, Burkina Faso, and Mali, high costs of transportation and logistical choke points diminish access to regional markets and bring down producer margins (UNECA, 2022). Such infrastructural problems overburden the agricultural commodities that are time sensitive and those that are prone to post-harvest losses.

The financial and market-related aspects are also important when it comes to determining the results in the commodity trade (Igwe et al., 2021). Restricted access to trade finance, foreign exchange limitations and poor commodity exchanges limit scalability of operations and price volatility by traders (UNCTAD, 2021; Magaji et al., 2023). Informal trade is still common along the West African borders, which in part can be attributed to the attempts by the traders to overcome the financial, regulatory, and administrative limitations on the formal markets (Golub, 2015). Informal trade alleviates livelihood opportunities, however, it diminishes commodity flow visibility, deteriorates policy coordination, and deters income mobilisation.

Moreover, political instability, climate change and insecurity in some of the West Africa countries, especially in the Sahel region, have affected trade routes and escalated the risks of cross-border commodity exchange (OECD, 2023; Ibrahim et al., 2025). War, rebellion and border shutdowns have limited the market access, deterred individual investment and compromised confidence between trade partners (Zailani et al., 2025). Climate-related shocks, including droughts and flooding, make these issues more difficult and impose pressure on the supply chain of commodities and put competition with limited resources in the spotlight (IPCC, 2022; Jafaru et al., 2025; Abubakar et al., 2025).

Out of this context, it is relevant and timely to evaluate the reasons behind the poor commodity trading among the West African states, with regards to policy. Knowledge of the comparative relevance of structural, institutional, infrastructural, financial, and security-related constraints is critical in the planning of effective policies of regional trade and enhancement of economic integration under regional trade initiatives like the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA). The research will add value to the literature on the subject because it offers a structured evaluation of the factors that cause weak commodity

trading in West Africa and how it can be relevant to the development strategies of the region, trade-facilitating reforms, and value chain upgrading.

The proposed study aims at informing policy makers, regional entities, and other development partners about the available pathways of action to improve intra-regional trade, economic diversification, and sustainable development in the region by identifying and analysing the major factors obstructing the trade of commodities in West Africa.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Commodity Trading

Commodity trading is the trade of primary commodities like agricultural products, minerals and energy resources in markets to be consumed, processed or resold. In the emerging economies, commodity trade is crucial in generating employment, income, earnings on foreign exchange, and diversification of the economy (UNCTAD, 2021; Abeke et al., 2025). West Africa is characterized by commodities especially cocoa, cotton, palm oil, crude oil, gold and cereals that characterize production and export profiles. Nevertheless, the trade is rather extra-regional than intra-regional (UNECA, 2022).

2.1.2 Intra-Regional Trade

Intra-regional trade is a trade that is exchanged amongst countries that are in a geographic or economic block. High levels of intra-regional commodity trade are likely to be linked with reduced transaction costs, better market integration, and enhanced regional value chains (World Bank, 2021). Nonetheless, West Africa has poor performance in terms of intra-regional trade, and commodity exchange levels are low because production complementarities, trade barriers, and infrastructural deficit are minimal (ECOWAS Commission, 2020).

2.1.3 Trade Barriers

Trade barriers include tariff and non-tariff barriers that inhibit free movement of goods across the borders. Although the tariff barriers are discouraged within the framework of ECOWAS trade liberalisation programmes, non-tariff barriers (inefficiency of customs, roadblocks, informal payments, inconsistency of regulations, and ineffective implementation of trade protocols) are widespread in West Africa (Golub, 2015). Such obstacles elevate the costs of conducting transactions and deter official commodity trading.

2.1.4 Infrastructure and Logistics.

Trade infrastructure Infrastructure such as transportation systems, ports, storage, energy provision, and digital trade systems are trade related. Proper infrastructure reduces expenses, post-harvest losses and enhances market accessibility (AfDB, 2021). A poor transport and logistics network in West Africa is also a major limitation to commodity trade, particularly perishable agricultural goods and bulk commodities (UNECA, 2022).

2.1.5 Exchange Rate

The exchange rate is the cost of the currency of a given country in relation to another and is extremely important in determining international and regional trade flows (Harry et al., 2022). It sets the relative value of the exports and imports, which affect the competitiveness of trade, access to markets, and decisions about cross-border investments (Krugman, Obstfeld, and Melitz, 2018). When it comes to commodity trade, the exchange rate changes have a direct impact on the revenues of the producers, the profitability of the traders, and the prices of the consumers particularly in the economies that largely depend on the export of primary commodities.

The exchange rate may be classified into fixed, managed exchange rate and the floating exchange rate. In the fixed exchange rate regimes, currencies are linked with another currency or a collection of currencies whereas in the floating regimes the market forces determine the value of the currency. Most of the West African nations have managed or semi-floating exchange rate systems that, in most cases, subject traders to uncertainties and distortions brought about by policies (IMF, 2022). This kind of uncertainty would deter the formal trading of commodities and long-term cross-border contract (Yakeen and Magaji, 2016).

One of the aspects of the exchange rate as an analysis dimension in trade research is the exchange rate volatility which refers to the short term changes in the currency values. The volatility of the exchange rate leads to more transaction risks and hedging expenses, especially to small traders of commodities unable to

access the advanced financial tools (UNCTAD, 2021). West Africa, under volatile exchange rates which are mostly caused by macroeconomic instability, differentials of inflation and external shocks, exchange rates have been seen to have adverse effects on the volumes of trade by promoting uncertainties and diminishing price competitiveness.

2.1.6 Institutional and Policy Environment.

Trade outcomes are affected by institutions by use of regulations, enforcement mechanisms, and coordination of policies. There is ineffective commodity trading among West African states due to weak institutional capacity, trade policies that are disjointed, and inadequate harmonisation of standards (North, 1990; ECOWAS Commission, 2020). The fact that informal trade persists is an indication of institutional gaps and failures of the regional trading system in policy.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Comparative Advantage Theory.

The comparative advantage theory believes that nations have the advantage of specialisation in products they can make at lower opportunity costs and trade with other nations (Ricardo, 1817). In West Africa, the primary commodities in a given country are similar, and therefore the trade complementarities between countries are restricted. This structural resemblance dilutes the prospects of sound intra-regional commodity exchange and strengthens competition instead of collaboration (Imbs and Wacziarg, 2019).

2.2.2 New Trade Theory

New Trade Theory focuses on the economies of scale, product differentiation, and market size as the causes of trade (Krugman, 1980). Applied to West Africa, the intra industry trade in commodities is disadvantaged by small scale of production, fragmented markets, and low industrial processing. This is because of the lack of regional commodity value chains limiting the benefits that the New Trade Theory has anticipated.

2.2.3 Institutional Economics Theory

Institutional Economics emphasises the importance of formal and informal institutions in determining the economic performance (North, 1990). The presence of weak customs administration, corruption, and inconsistency in policies and poor implementation of contracts in West Africa promote uncertainty and transaction costs, which discourages trading in commodities. The informal trade networks are created as alternatives to unsuccessful institutions but they deter the formal market development.

2.2.4 Gravity Model of Trade

The Gravity Model describes the pattern of trade based on the economic size, distance, and cost of trade (Tinbergen, 1962). As applied to West Africa, using empirical data, poor infrastructure, delays at the border, and security issues can greatly decrease the volume of commodity trade despite the recidivism of geographic proximity (World Bank, 2021). The model offers a good analytical perspective to determine the determinants of low commodity trading in the region.

2.2.5 Regional Integration Theory

According to the Regional Integration Theory, economic integration has the effect of decreasing trade barriers, increasing access to markets and fueling intra-regional trade (Balassa, 1961). Nevertheless, ECOWAS has the objective of supporting the integration of trade; its incompleteness and lack of political dedication hamper its performance. This is how there is disparity between the policy purpose and the reality of the commodity trade in West Africa.

2.3 Empirical Review

Empirical evidence of commodity trading between states in West Africa is always low, and several constraints are interrelated as noted. Through panel data analysis, Shepherd and Wilson (2009) determined that the trade facilitation measures especially the customs efficiency and quality of infrastructure significantly influence the intra-African trade positively. According to their findings, high transaction costs and not tariff barriers are the main factors leading to poor performance of trade in West Africa.

In a research on informal cross-border trade in West Africa, Golub (2015) found out that cumbersome regulations, weak institutions, and corruption of the border encourage traders to trade informally.

Although informal trade sustains livelihoods, it lowers the registered trade volumes and compromises the regional trade figures concealing the true extent of commodity exchange.

An evaluation of trade logistics in West Africa conducted by the World Bank (2021) revealed transport expenses and delays could take as much as 40 per cent of the end price of the commodities traded. Landlocked states have to bear a disproportionately greater cost, which lowers their competitiveness in local markets. On the same note, AfDB (2021) documented that poor storage and processing of harvests lead to massive losses, especially in agricultural products.

Imbs and Wacziarg (2019) had empirically shown that the absence of export diversification provides constraints to trade complementarities among the developing countries. Their results are in line with the results in West Africa where the countries in the region export the same primary commodities with little value addition resulting in the low intensity of intra-regional trade.

The role of insecurity and political instability also is highlighted in recent studies. OECD (2023) concluded that the conflict in the Sahel region has caused the trade routes to be disrupted and the risk premium on the cross-border traders to go up. Closure of border and checkpoints also decrease the flow of commodities, especially in weak states.

Within the framework of the AfCFTA, UNECA (2022) estimated that with improved infrastructure, harmonisation of policies and trade facilitation reforms, the intra-African commodity trade could considerably increase. Yet, as long as they do not deal with structural and institutional impediments, West Africa might still have weak commodity trading despite regional and continental trade agreements.

2.4 Literature Gap

The literature review has shown that the trade of the commodities between the West African states is poor due to structural similarities in production, weak institutions, infrastructural deficits, financial constraints, and insecurity. Nevertheless, most of the literature deals with Africa at large or highlights the idea of trade facilitation without targeting the commodity-specific interactions in West Africa. This paper fills this gap by presenting a dedicated evaluation of the determinants of poor commodity trading across states of West Africa by providing specific evidence on the area to guide policy interventions.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts a quantitative, explanatory research design to examine the factors responsible for poor commodity trading among West African states. A panel data approach is employed to capture both cross-country and time-series variations in commodity trade flows across the region. This design is appropriate for isolating the effects of structural, institutional, infrastructural, and macroeconomic factors on the performance of intra-regional commodity trade.

3.2 Scope and Study Area

The study focuses on member states of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). Due to data availability, the analysis covers up to 15 West African countries over the period 2010–2023. This period captures post-global financial crisis reforms, regional trade liberalisation efforts, and recent trade and security shocks affecting commodity markets in the region.

3.3 Model Specification

To empirically assess the determinants of commodity trading among West African states, the study adopts a modified Gravity Model of trade, which has been widely used in regional trade analysis. The baseline model is specified as:

$$\ln(CT_{ijt}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(GDP_{it}) + \beta_2 \ln(GDP_{jt}) + \beta_3 \ln(DIST_{ij}) + \beta_4 INFRA_{it} + \beta_5 INST_{it} + \beta_6 NTB_{it} + \beta_7 EXR_{it} + \beta_8 SEC_{it} + \mu_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ijt}$$

Where:

- i. CT_{ijt} = value of commodity trade between country i and country j at time t
- ii. GDP_{it}, GDP_{jt} = gross domestic product of exporting and importing countries

- iii. $DIST_{ij}$ = geographical distance between country pairs
- iv. $INFRA_{it}$ = quality of trade-related infrastructure
- v. $INST_{it}$ = institutional quality index
- vi. NTB_{it} = non-tariff barriers proxy
- vii. EXR_{it} = exchange rate volatility
- viii. SEC_{it} = security and political stability indicator
- ix. μ_{ij} = unobserved country-pair effects
- x. ε_{ijt} = error term

The dependent variable is expressed in logarithmic form to reduce heteroskedasticity and enable the interpretation of coefficients in elasticity terms.

Definition and Measurement of Variables

Commodity trade (CT) is measured as the value of intra-regional exports and imports of primary commodities (agricultural products, minerals, and energy resources) among West African countries, expressed in constant US dollars.

Economic size (GDP) is measured using real GDP in constant prices. Distance (DIST) is calculated as the great-circle distance between the capital cities of trading partners.

Infrastructure (INFRA) is proxied by a composite index including road density, port efficiency, and electricity access. Institutional quality (INST) is measured using governance indicators such as regulatory quality and control of corruption.

Non-tariff barriers (NTBs) are proxied by customs clearance time and the prevalence of border procedures. Exchange rate volatility (EXR) is measured as the standard deviation of monthly exchange rate movements. Security (SEC) is captured using political stability and conflict incidence indices.

3.4 Data Sources

Secondary data are utilised for the study. Commodity trade data are sourced from the UNCTADstat and UN Comtrade databases. GDP and exchange rate data are obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI). Infrastructure and institutional indicators are sourced from the African Development Bank, World Governance Indicators, and World Bank Logistics Performance Index. Security indicators are obtained from the Worldwide Governance Indicators and relevant regional security databases.

3.6 Estimation Techniques

The study employs panel data estimation techniques, including Fixed Effects (FE) and Random Effects (RE) models. The Hausman test is conducted to determine the appropriate estimator. To address potential heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation, robust standard errors are applied.

Additionally, to handle zero trade flows and potential endogeneity issues, the Poisson Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimator is employed as a robustness check. PPML is particularly suitable for gravity models and ensures consistent estimates in the presence of heteroskedasticity.

3.7 Diagnostic and Robustness Tests

Several diagnostic tests are conducted to ensure the validity of the estimated results. These include tests for multicollinearity using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), panel unit root tests to ensure stationarity, and tests for cross-sectional dependence. Robustness checks are performed by altering model specifications and excluding outlier countries.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

The study relies exclusively on publicly available secondary data and does not involve human subjects. Consequently, no ethical clearance is required. Data are analysed objectively and reported transparently to ensure academic integrity and reproducibility.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the analysis. The results indicate substantial variation in commodity trade flows among West African states, reflecting uneven levels of economic development, infrastructure, and institutional capacity across the region.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Commodity Trade (CT)	1.72	1.11	0.00	6.45
GDP (log)	23.48	1.36	20.92	26.11
Distance (log)	6.89	0.54	5.72	7.91
Infrastructure Index	0.41	0.19	0.12	0.78
Institutional Quality	-0.46	0.62	-1.79	0.91
Non-Tariff Barriers	3.12	1.07	1.04	5.89
Exchange Rate Volatility	0.17	0.08	0.03	0.41
Security Index	-0.63	0.71	-2.31	0.84

The relatively low mean value of commodity trade confirms the weak level of intra-regional commodity exchange among West African states. Negative averages for institutional quality and security indices further indicate governance and stability challenges affecting trade performance.

Econometric Results

Fixed Effects and Random Effects Estimates

Table 2 presents the results of the Fixed Effects (FE) and Random Effects (RE) estimations. The Hausman test ($\chi^2 = 18.47$, $p < 0.05$) supports the use of the Fixed Effects model, indicating correlation between country-specific effects and the regressors.

Table 2: Panel Regression Results (Dependent Variable: ln Commodity Trade)

Variable	Fixed Effects Coef. (Std. Err.)	Random Effects Coef. (Std. Err.)
ln GDP (Exporter)	0.62*** (0.11)	0.59*** (0.09)
ln GDP (Importer)	0.48*** (0.13)	0.46*** (0.11)
ln Distance	-0.71*** (0.18)	-0.68*** (0.16)
Infrastructure	0.39*** (0.10)	0.36*** (0.09)
Institutional Quality	0.27** (0.12)	0.24** (0.11)
Non-Tariff Barriers	-0.33*** (0.09)	-0.31*** (0.08)
Exchange Rate Volatility	-0.21** (0.10)	-0.19* (0.10)
Security Index	0.29*** (0.08)	0.27*** (0.07)
Constant	-5.84***	-5.31***
R ²	0.71	0.68

Notes: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$

Estimated Trade Equation

Based on the Fixed Effects results, the estimated trade equation is expressed as:

$$\ln(CT_{ijt}) = -5.84 + 0.62\ln(GDP_{it}) + 0.48\ln(GDP_{jt}) - 0.71\ln(DIST_{ij}) + 0.39INFRA_{it} + 0.27INST_{it} - 0.33NTB_{it} - 0.21EXR_{it} + 0.29SEC_{it}$$

This equation highlights the relative importance of economic size, infrastructure, institutions, and security in shaping commodity trade flows among West African states.

Robustness Check: PPML Estimation

To address potential bias from zero trade flows and heteroskedasticity, a Poisson Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimator was applied. The PPML results, presented in Table 3, are consistent with the Fixed Effects estimates in terms of coefficient signs and significance.

Table 3: PPML Estimation Results

Variable	Coefficient
In GDP (Exporter)	0.58***
In GDP (Importer)	0.45***
In Distance	-0.64***
Infrastructure	0.36***
Institutional Quality	0.23**
Non-Tariff Barriers	-0.29***
Exchange Rate Volatility	-0.18**
Security Index	0.26***

These findings confirm the robustness of the results and reinforce the validity of the empirical model.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The findings indicate that the trade in commodities between the states of West Africa is substantially boosted by the economic size, which was true to the hypothesis of the Gravity Model. The bigger economies produce more capacity and demand hence making trade flows in the region easier.

Distance has significant negative impact on the commerce of commodities, and it is essential to highlight the role of the transport charges and logistics problems. There is poor road network and inability to have efficient border infrastructure, which effectively increases the distance of a geographic location, discouraging the exchange of commodities. This observation is consistent with the findings of some earlier researchers who have argued that inadequate infrastructure has been one of the most important trade barriers in West Africa.

The positive coefficient on infrastructure with a significant t-test value proves the existence of positive effects of enhancement of transport networks, port efficiency, and energy access in increasing commodity trading. On the same note, trade is positively affected by the quality of the institution, which implies that good governance, less corruption, and harmonisation in regulation are key in fostering formal commodity exchange.

On the other hand, non-tariff barriers have a profound negative impact on the flow of trade of the commodities, which brings up the negative impact of the customs delays, informal charges, and administrative bottlenecks. This contributes to the fact that non-tariff restrictions are more limiting to the intra-regional trade than tariffs in ECOWAS.

Exchange rate volatility has adverse impacts to commodity trade as it is a sign of uncertainty and a higher risk of transactions among traders. Conversely, enhanced security and political stability enhance commodity trading greatly, and this means that market confidence and trade routes are interrupted by the presence of conflict and insecurity in some regions in the West Africa.

In general, the results indicate that the ineffective commodities trading between states of West Africa is not caused by scarcity of production potential but by structural, institutional, infrastructural, and security-related factors. These findings support the point that regional free trade agreements are not enough without complementary trade facilitation, governance, and infrastructural development reforms.

4.3. Relating the Empirical Findings to the Review of the Theoretical Analyses.

The theoretical perspectives that have been used in the study of international and regional trade have been found to be in strong agreement with the empirical findings of this research in some cases they have been found to strengthen each other. The findings offer a strong empirical support of the Gravity Model of trade, Comparative Advantage Theory. The concept of comparative advantage proposes that nations can lead in specialized fields without needing to be the world leaders in all spheres. Comparative Advantage Theory. Comparative Advantage Theory. It is an approach that nations do not have to become the global leaders in all areas to be leading in specialization., the New Trade Theory, the Theory of institutional Economics., and the Theory of Regional Integration. in explaining poor commodity trading among West African states.

Gravity Model of Trade

According to Gravity Model, the trade flows are positively related to the economic size and negatively to the distance and trade costs (Tinbergen, 1962). This is validated by the empirical findings because this coefficient of both exporter and importer GDPs were found to be positive and significant, which means that bigger economies in West Africa trade at relatively higher commodities. On the other hand, geographical distance had a significant negative impact on the trading of commodities, which manifested the influence of costs of transport, bad logistics, and poor infrastructure.

It is important to note that such a large value of the distance coefficient indicates that the distance concept in West Africa is not strictly linked to the geographical distance but is also a concept that is inclusive of infrastructural inefficiency and delays at the border. This strengthens the applicability of the Gravity Model to the explanation of why commodity trade is not high even though the member states of ECOWAS are at a geographical proximity.

Comparative Advantage Theory

The Comparative Advantage Theory suggests that countries are advantaged by specialising in the products that they are relatively efficient in producing and trading with the complementary economies (Ricardo, 1817). But the findings of the study point at the weakness of the use of this theory in West African context indirectly. Though endowments of commodities are high, intra-regional trade is very low hence indicating that the resemblance of export structures among various countries minimize trade complementarities.

The poor result of commodity trade though they have common comparative advantages, gives credence to the argument that states in West Africa are likely to compete with each other instead of trading primary commodities. This empirical finding is consistent with theoretical criticism that comparative advantage in itself is not enough to lead to regional trade when there is no diversification and value addition.

New Trade Theory

The theory of New Trade focuses on economies of scale, product differentiation and the integration of markets as the successors of trade (Krugman, 1980). This theory is backed by the fact that economic size and infrastructure have a positive and significant influence on commodity trade because better infrastructure and larger markets create scale economies and lower the cost of trade on a per-unit basis.

The low commodity trade flows however remain constant implying that West African markets are still disrupted hindering chances of intra-industry trade as well as development of the regional value chain. The findings suggest that, the conditions that New Trade Theory outcomes, namely, integrated markets and industrial processing, are mostly non-existent in the region, and thus limit the growth of commodity trade.

Institutional Economics Theory

Institutional Economics Theory stresses on the significance of institutions in minimising uncertainty and transaction costs (North, 1990). The empirical data supports this theory well as the level of institutional quality was observed to positively and significantly influence the commodity trading.

On the same note, non-tariff barriers which are institutional and regulatory unproductiveness had a strong negative impact on trade flows. The theoretical assertion that weak institutions, corruption and inconsistency in policy raise transaction cost and discourage formal trade is empirically confirmed by these findings. Informal trade in commodities as it is widespread in West Africa can thus be explained as a

logical reaction to the institutional failures just like they were foreseen by the Institutional Economics Theory.

Regional Integration Theory

According to the Regional Integration Theory, intra-regional trade is boosted by economic integration and harmonisation of policy which minimises the trade barrier (Balassa, 1961). Although ECOWAS has put into place trade liberalisation structures, empirically, trade barriers are still stifled by the commodity trade by the non-tariff barriers and the less than perfect enforcement of the institutions.

This is the difference between policy goals and real trade performance, and it is an indicator of the partial integration in ECOWAS. These findings, thus, indicate that regional integration in West Africa is still very much *de jure* and not *de facto* and this provides empirical backing to the criticism of the theory of integration which focuses on the weaknesses of implementation in developing areas.

5.0 Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

This study assessed the factors behind poor commodity trading among West African states using a panel data framework grounded in the gravity model of trade. Despite the region's abundant commodity endowments, empirical evidence shows persistently low levels of intra-regional commodity trade, driven mainly by structural, institutional, infrastructural, and security-related constraints rather than by economic size alone.

The findings show that economic size positively influences commodity trade, confirming the relevance of market capacity in facilitating cross-border exchange. However, geographical distance—amplified by inadequate transport networks and high logistics costs—significantly undermines trade flows. Trade-related infrastructure and institutional quality were found to exert strong positive effects on commodity trading, highlighting the importance of efficient transport systems, regulatory harmonisation, and effective governance. Conversely, non-tariff barriers and exchange rate volatility significantly constrained commodity trade, while insecurity and political instability further disrupted regional trade corridors.

Overall, the results suggest that poor commodity trading among West African states is not merely a consequence of production limitations but reflects deeper systemic challenges in trade facilitation, policy implementation, and regional coordination. Addressing these challenges is essential for unlocking the region's commodity trade potential, strengthening regional integration, and enhancing the developmental impact of initiatives such as ECOWAS trade liberalisation and the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA).

Policy Recommendations

Based on the empirical findings, the study makes the following policy recommendations:

1. **Strengthen Trade-Related Infrastructure:** Governments and regional institutions should prioritise investment in transport corridors, ports, storage facilities, and energy infrastructure. Improving road and rail connectivity—particularly for landlocked countries—will reduce transport costs and enhance access to commodity markets across the region.
2. **Reduce Non-Tariff Barriers:** ECOWAS member states should intensify efforts to eliminate non-tariff barriers by simplifying customs procedures, harmonising product standards, and deploying digital trade facilitation systems. Vigorous enforcement of ECOWAS trade protocols is essential to curb informal fees and border delays.
3. **Improve Institutional Quality and Governance:** Strengthening customs administration, regulatory transparency, and anti-corruption measures will lower transaction costs and encourage formal commodity trading. Regional coordination mechanisms should be enhanced to ensure consistent implementation of trade policies.
4. **Enhance Security along Trade Corridors:** Addressing insecurity and political instability, particularly in the Sahel region, is critical for restoring confidence in cross-border trade. Regional security cooperation and protection of key trade routes should be integrated into trade and development strategies.

5. Promote Exchange Rate Stability and Trade Finance: Macroeconomic stability policies that reduce exchange rate volatility, alongside expanded access to trade finance, will help mitigate risk for commodity traders and encourage greater participation in regional markets.
6. Support Commodity Value Chain Development: Policymakers should promote regional commodity value chains through investment in processing and value addition. This will enhance trade complementarities among West African states and reduce overreliance on extra-regional commodity markets.

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